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Traditional Gender Roles, Consumption, and the Globalized World: An Analysis of *Eat Drink Man Woman*

Geleneksel Cinsiyet Rollerini, Tüketim ve Globalleşen Dünya: *Eat Drink Man Woman*'ın Bir Analizi

ABSTRACT

Inequalities between men and women have a long history. Emerged in the eighteenth century in order to eliminate the disadvantages of being female and achieve gender equality with men, feminism has always aimed to change the status quo and abandon patriarchy to create a more equal administration. Although there have lately been significant improvements in achieving gender equality in a wide range of areas worldwide, especially since the last quarter of the twentieth century, feminist thought has continuously sought ways to overcome various obstacles that women face and create a better world for women. Traditional gender roles and their organization are essential issues that feminist ideas and views generally elaborate on. These traditional gender roles, including how the family is organized in societies as the smallest part, have inevitably changed and become subjects of reformation in the same era. Furthermore, capitalism has gained power and led to social results, as it has directed how people spend money and increased consumption. Capitalism also brought globalization, which connected various locations and societies worldwide, signaling a new culture that tends to abandon traditional values and create a different way of thought and living. In this paper, the movie *Eat Drink Man Woman* (originally titled *Yin Shi Nan Nu*) will be analysed regarding traditional gender roles, consumption culture, and globalization. The movie explicitly references these concepts and represents how they shape people's lives in various ways.

Keywords: Traditional Gender Roles, Consumption, Globalization.

ÖZET

Erkekler ve kadınlar arasındaki eşitsizlikler uzun bir geçmişe sahiptir. Kadın olmanın dezavantajlarını ortadan kaldırmak ve erkeklerle cinsiyet eşitliği sağlamak amacıyla on sekizinci yüzyılda ortaya çıkan feminizm, her zaman statükoyu değiştirmeyi ve daha eşit bir yönetim yaratmak için ataerkilliği bir kenara bırakmayı amaçlamıştır. Özellikle yirminci yüzyılın son çeyreğinden bu yana, dünya çapında çok çeşitli alanlarda cinsiyet eşitliğini sağlama yolunda önemli gelişmeler yaşanmış olsa da feminist düşünce kadınların karşılaştığı çeşitli engelleri aşmanın ve kadınlar için daha iyi bir dünya yaratmanın yollarını sürekli olarak aramıştır. Geleneksel cinsiyet rolleri ve bunların organize edilmesi, feminist fikir ve görüşlerin genellikle üzerinde durduğu temel konulardır. Ailenin toplumlarda en küçük parça olarak nasıl organize edildiği de dahil olmak üzere bu geleneksel cinsiyet rolleri kaçınılmaz olarak değişmiş ve aynı dönemde reformların konusu haline gelmiştir. Aynı zamanda, kapitalizm de güç kazanmış ve insanların para harcamalarını yönlendirdiği ve tüketimi artırdığı için çeşitli toplumsal sonuçlara yol açmıştır. Kapitalizm ayrıca, dünya çapında çeşitli yerleri ve toplumları birbirine bağlayan, geleneksel değerleri terk etme ve farklı bir düşünce ve yaşam biçimi yaratma eğiliminde olan yeni bir kültürü işaret eden küreselleşmeyi de beraberinde getirmiştir. Bu makalede, *Eat Drink Man Woman* (orijinali *Yin Shi Nan Nu*) filmi geleneksel cinsiyet rolleri, tüketim kültürü ve küreselleşme açısından analiz edilecektir. Film bu kavramlara açıkça atıfta bulunmakta ve bunların insanların hayatlarını çeşitli şekillerde nasıl şekillendirdiğini göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Geleneksel Cinsiyet Rollerini, Tüketim, Globalleşme.

1. INTRODUCTION

Although women and men are meant to experience and share life together in every aspect, unfortunately, significant inequalities have always persisted between them worldwide. Since the last quarter of the twentieth century, feminist views and ideas have highlighted gender inequality and produced arguments that have led to various discussions on overcoming this issue to achieve gender equality in societies. Meanwhile, with the inevitable impact of capitalism, rapidly increasing consumption trends have become integral parts of social dynamics with globalization. Traditional gender roles are a significant part of how a society is organized. As the family is known to be the smallest part of society, changes are most easily observed on the family scale. In this paper, the movie *Eat Drink Man Woman* (originally titled *Yin Shi Nan Nu*) will be analysed regarding traditional gender roles, consumption culture, and globalization.

2. ABOUT THE MOVIE

2.1. The Story

Eat Drink Man Woman (1994), directed by Ang Lee, is about a family living in Taipei that goes through essential changes in their lives and how they react to those events in their ways with the other people around them. The family consists of the father (Chu) and his three daughters (Jia-Jen, Jian-Chien, and Jia-Ning). Chu is a master chef in a big restaurant's kitchen. After the death of their mothers, the girls have chosen different paths. Jia-Jen is a Christian and a chemistry teacher. Jia-Chien works as an airline executive, and Jia-Ning is still a student who works in a fast-food restaurant in her free time. They all seem to lead very different and busy lives themselves; however, they come together every Sunday night for dinner at the table ritualistically, symbolizing their love and care for each other. Girls usually use those gatherings to communicate with their father and announce the new things in their lives during those nights. The movie represents a section of their lives.

2.2. The Main Characters

Chu: He is an old man who lost his wife a long time ago and had to raise his three daughters alone. He works as a master chef at a big restaurant and is interested in traditional rather than fast food, which is becoming increasingly common. However, he sadly states that he has lost his sense of taste a while ago. Furthermore, he seems to give much importance to traditional family values and tries to keep his family together. For that aim, he prepares special conventional dishes for dinner every Sunday night, and all the family gathers around the table. Later, he marries their widowed neighbor after the events are resolved.

Jia-Jen: She works at a high school teaching Chemistry. After breaking up with his long-time boyfriend at college, she has been very sad about it. Furthermore, being the family's oldest child, she feels like everyone pressures her to get married as soon as possible. Someone at her school makes fun of her writing love letters, and she gets angry. Later, she meets another teacher who has recently begun to work there and becomes interested in him. They quickly get married; she tells her family about him and her marriage at a Sunday night dinner at the table.

Jia-Chien: She is the middle child of the family. She likes to cook and enjoys it as much as her father. However, she feels like her father did not let her become a chef because he feared that she would be better than he was. Instead, he sent her to college, and she was able to work at a big firm. She lives more independently and attempts to buy a flat in a big housing complex. After a while, she discovers that she has become a fraud victim as the construction company's owners have run away with the cash they have gotten from the clients. Later, thanks to her hard work, she is promoted to vice president for the Amsterdam branch of her company. After a while of deciding, she finally relocates there. Furthermore, it is not true that her father was not afraid of her success as a chef; he sent her to college so that she could have a better future in globalization. In the finale, her father can taste the food she cooks, which makes him incredibly happy, proving that her father did not have patriarchal concerns about not letting her become a chef like himself.

Jia-Ning: She is the youngest child of the family. In addition to school, she works at a fast-food restaurant. Suddenly, she becomes interested in her friend's boyfriend. He breaks up with the other, and they get together. After a while, she announces her relationship and pregnancy to her family at a Sunday night dinner and leaves the house to live with her boyfriend.

3. ANALYSIS OF THE MOVIE

3.1. Traditional Gender Roles

Gender-related issues occupy a significant part of the scenario. Considering the movie from a feminist perspective, it represents several situations referring to the masculinity and domestic and social roles of genders, with a focus on family structure.

Senior Chef Chu symbolizes the masculine power and men's dominance in the movie. His workspace and how he handles work represent those (Figure 1). All the staff in the restaurant's kitchen consists of men. This scene includes concepts from the masculine list of Linda McDowell: public, outside, work, production, independence, and power (McDowell, 1999) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. His colleagues consult Chef Chu about a problem that occurs during the preparation of a big dinner party at the restaurant

Despite his dominant position at work, Chef Chu seems to have a different position in her daughters' eyes. As a single father of three girls, he tries to handle the housework alone. There is a contrast between his work and private life, which can be interpreted as a result of changing or integrating previously assigned gender roles over time, perhaps due to the newly occurring need under new circumstances (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Chef Chu is serving his daughters their ritualistic Sunday dinner

Chef Chu's middle daughter, Jia-Chen, also represents an example of changing gender roles in the movie. Her father had realized her culinary talent before; however, he deliberately kept her away from the kitchen and sent her to college to let her have another job in which she could have a better life, in his view. Jia-Chen assumes that her father acted that way for a long time due to his patriarchal concerns. She discovers the truth when she hears it from his father's close friend and colleague. She is good at cooking and can even bring her father's sense of taste back after many years. This demonstrates that women can become good chefs as much as men can, considering the male dominance in the culinary arts and sector worldwide.

In addition to representing different gender roles, the movie interestingly depicts a traditional family in Taipei. In contrast to conventional values, Chef Chu's youngest daughter, Jia-Nin, announces that she is pregnant while they are at their dinner table, and her father can barely react to her confession. Later, he seems to accept the situation unconditionally. In this way, the movie also shows a new, changed family, different from the traditional ones.

3.2. Consumption Culture

The movie represents how consumption culture has emerged and evolved, where it takes place in Taipei, primarily focusing on food. There is a big contrast between how traditional food is served by Chef Chu (Figure 3) and how fast food is prepared and sold where Jia-Ning works at a mall (Figure 4). In addition to the fact that it is prepared differently, in this case, fast food restaurants provide new ways for consumers to consume (Ritzer, 1996). As in Figure 4, they are usually very crowded. Such new ways of consumption urge people to consume more and more (Baudrillard, 2004), contributing to the expansion of the consumption culture of our time.

Figure 3. Chef Chu prepares a meal in his home kitchen

Figure 4. People buy fast food in a hurry from the fast food restaurant where Jia-Ning works

Figure 5. Chef Chu asks the little daughter of their neighbour about what she eats for breakfast

Figure 6. Chef Chu brings the little girl lunch to her classroom

Food, with how it is prepared and consumed, is an essential part of the movie and for the message that the film aims to convey to the audience. Chef Chu is very concerned about what their neighbor's daughter eats at school (Figure 5). She even complains to him that she does not have enough time to have a proper breakfast at home in the mornings. When Chu learns that she will buy her lunch from the school cafeteria, he kindly offers to bring her lunch (Figure 6). In this way, he thinks that she will have better nutrition as a child. The little girl likes her meals, which Chef Chu prepares so much that she even wants him to cook for her friends in the class, preparing a list of names.

The consumption culture represented in the movie can also be interpreted as an inevitable result of post-modernism and capitalism. Chef Chu tries to hold on to the traditional food of his country and his lifelong experiences as a chef while he complies that his youngest daughter works at a fast food restaurant. In different circumstances, he might not approve of that; however, the conditions of the new post-modernist world and the need for employment and money concerning capitalism seem to make him accept that. Furthermore, he somehow manages to act against capitalism in his own way by preparing homemade traditional food for his neighbor's daughter. In this case, post-modernism, capitalism, and consumption culture feed each other, and the results of each lead to the other.

Besides food, in terms of architecture, the movie shows how people are tempted to buy flats in massive housing complexes. Jia-Chien uses all her money to buy a flat and feels happy and proud. However, it turns out that the company has been building at a site full of toxic material, and they vanished with all the money they had. She discovers all these when she goes there with her friend to show him her future flat (Figure 7). This can also be seen as a negative result of the consumption culture and capitalism, which urge people to have things.

Figure 7. Jia-Chien and her friend are at the construction site for her future flat

3.3. Globalization

In the movie, the family's middle child, Jia-Chien, works as an airline executive. Located in Taipei, they have branches in different parts of the world, including Amsterdam, where the director later wants to send Jia-Chien. They even plan to establish new routes, such as Sydney to Bangkok, to compete with the American airline companies. These show the impact of globalization. Globalization is closely related to geography (King, 2004). Air travel incredibly eases travelling between two destinations; therefore, in this case, globalization makes the world a single place (Robertson, 1995). Considering transportation activity, globalization can also be described as a relatively communicational concept, with the new communication systems, we now have a more developed communication network (Jameson, 1998).

Jia-Chien's story best fits the movie's themes of globalization. With her father's decision, she now has a more "global" job instead of becoming a traditional chef in her country. In the end, she accepts the promotion her director awards her and moves to Amsterdam for her new position in the company's branch there.

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, *Eat Drink Man Woman* is a movie that sheds light on traditional gender roles, consumption, and globalization based on the story of a conventional family. The film successfully demonstrates how these concepts operate and play a role in the changes and evolution of the postmodern world under different circumstances.

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